

Synthesis of CMC matrix by nitridation of TiSi_2 .

J. Roger*, L. Maillé, M.A. Dourges

Université Bordeaux 1, Laboratoire des Composites ThermoStructuraux,
UMR 5801, 33600 Pessac, France

* Corresponding author (roger@lcts.u-bordeaux1.fr)

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1 Introduction

Since several decades, ceramic matrix composites are developed for aeronautical and spatial applications [1]. Due to their high thermal resistance and their low density this kind of material is useful especially in the hot parts of engines. These composites are usually elaborated by infiltrating a woven preform by chemical vapor infiltration to form a ceramic matrix. Other processes can also be used to form the matrix. In particular ceramic processes in which a slurry impregnation including filler powder and liquid polymer can be used [2-4]. The active fillers are aimed at reducing the volume shrinkage resulting from the pyrolytic conversion of polymer to ceramic (Fig. 1) [5,6]. Si_3N_4 -based materials represent one of the most promising structural materials owing to their high heat resistance, hardness, chemical resistance and good oxidation resistance [7]. In this context, titanium disilicide TiSi_2 was identified as interesting active filler: under nitrogen atmosphere, the nitridation of this phase starts in a temperature range around 1000°C to form TiN and Si_3N_4 (Fig. 2) generating a 57% volume increase [8]. This property was previously used to produce efficient self-aligned diffusion barrier from nitridation of TiSi_2 in the temperature range 900-1000°C for durations comprised between 60 seconds to 60 minutes, the so-obtained phases were TiN and silicon that reacts with nitrogen very slowly at these temperatures [9-11]. TiN- Si_3N_4 composites represent an interesting combination with specific properties: high strength, low density, electrical conductivity [12]. This kind of composites can be easily obtained by self-propagating high temperature synthesis (SHS) under nitrogen atmosphere [13]. Nevertheless, the temperatures can reach values above 2000°C during the process, what is incompatible with the production of SiC-fiber composites due to the

relatively low thermal stability of the SiC fibers (Nicalon fibers) that became unstable at temperature above 1100°C. It is then necessary to work at a maximum temperature of 1100°C. Several previous studies were realized on the nitridation of silicon powders that detailed the effects of the main controlling factors: temperature [14-17], particle shape and size [16], impurities in the sample and in the atmosphere [18-20], composition of the atmosphere [21,22]. It appeared in this analogous subject that the definition of a general mechanism was laborious. Then, extensive and complete studies of the kinetic analysis of silicon nitridation were reported [20,22]. The kinetic and mechanism of titanium powders nitridation into TiN were also examined [24,25]. The results for synthesis up to 1000°C demonstrate that the complete conversion is possible after durations of only a few hours. The process of titanium nitridation indicates two steps: a rapid dissolution of nitrogen in α -Ti, and a slower heterogeneous reaction of the nitrogen-saturated α -Ti with N_2 to generate TiN [25]. The main aims of the study reported here were to complete the previous works [26] by identifying the influence of time, temperature and particles size on the TiSi_2 nitridation progression. The heat treatments were then realized under nitrogen principally at two different temperatures (1000 and 1100°C) and for two particles sizes (1.4 and 4.5 μm). The heating was maintained for long durations up to 100 hours.

2-Materials and experimental procedures

The TiSi_2 powder (99.95%, 44 μm , Neyco) used in these experiments was analyzed by spectrographic analysis to contain 1.64% O, 0.43% C and 0.48% Fe in mass. The raw powder was milled by two different ways: with a vibratory mixer mill (Retsch MM200), or with a planetary ball mill (Fritsch

Pulverisette 7). By these ways, two powders with mean sizes equal to 4.5 and 1.4 μm were obtained and used in the present work. The mean sizes of the powders were determined with the help of a Fritsch Analysette 22 Nanotec plus granulometric analyser. Nitridation processes were realized at normal pressure under a continuous nitrogen gas flow (50mL/min). The heating were performed in a furnace or in a thermogravimetric analyzer (Setaram TAG24) from 20°C to 1100°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min for various durations up to 100 hours. The powder masses used for thermogravimetric analysis were comprised between 100 and 110 mg. The powders treated in a furnace were destined to X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. Indeed, these diffraction experiments were used for phase identification and quantitative phase determination in samples of sufficient size (≥ 200 mg) which permitted accurate powder diffraction profiles to be obtained [27]. Each pattern was analyzed using the Rietveld [28] whole profile fitting method with the software Fullprof [29]. XRD experiments in Bragg-Brentano geometry were performed with a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer using a Cu K α radiation fitted with a one-dimensional position sensitive silicon strip detector (Bruker, Linxeye). XRD patterns were recorded using a step size of 0.01° for 2θ range 10-90° and a counting time of 0.3 second per step.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of the nitridation temperature

The milled powders were both nitrided at temperatures equal to 1000 or 1100°C for durations up to 100 hours. As clearly demonstrates by the Figures 3 and 4, it appears that the shapes and the maximum of the weight gain curves are very different. It is worth noting the very good agreement between the results of the two types of nitridation device. The stabilized maximum value measured at 1000°C is of 14.29% (1.4 μm) whereas the corresponding value at 1100°C is comprised between 25.22% (4.5 μm) and 31.69% (1.4 μm). For the same duration, the values at 1100°C are nearly twice than the ones at 1000°C, this revealed a strong dependence of the reactivity towards the applied temperature. This is confirmed by the phase's ratios

from Rietveld analysis (Fig. 5). Regardless of the particles sizes, the mass ratios of free silicon coming from the decomposition of the initial TiSi_2 are higher than 40% at 1000°C and the corresponding proportions of Si_3N_4 are barely detectable even for the highest duration. At 1100°C, the percentages of free silicon are clearly lower and decrease relatively rapidly depending on the powder size. Moreover, the mass percentages of Si_3N_4 are largely higher reaching values of about 8.0% and 55.0% after heating of only 50h. It is then very clear that silicon nitridation is strongly temperature dependant. This is evidently not the case for the nitridation of titanium. Indeed, in all cases titanium nitride TiN is rapidly synthesized with mass contents higher than 40%. This difference of behavior between silicon and titanium can be mainly justified by the following facts: considering the Ti-N phase diagram (Fig. 6), several phases can be formed within the 1000-1100°C temperature range i.e. metallic α -Ti and β -Ti and their solid solutions, the solid solution TiN_{1-x} and its nitrogen richest limit TiN . As a consequence, titanium coming from TiSi_2 decomposition can react with nitrogen through a mechanism that promotes a progressive increase of nitrogen within titanium. In fact, one can consider that metallic titanium captures progressively nitrogen atoms with structural transformations depending on the constituent ratio. When metallic titanium reaches its nitrogen richest limit, the addition of a few nitrogen atoms induces a modification of titanium crystallographic network from BCC to FCC, what authorized the nitrogen enrichment through the TiN_{1-x} solid solution (FCC) up to the formation of the richest nitrogen composition i.e. TiN . This stepped and progressive mechanism facilitates the formation of the TiN phase. This kind of mechanism is not possible with the case of the Si_3N_4 phase because there is no other phase and no solid solution in the Si-N system. Another important fact to take into account is the values of the self-diffusion coefficients of N, Si and Ti within the TiN and Si_3N_4 phases. As shows in the Figure 7, it appears that the self-diffusion coefficients of Si and N within Si_3N_4 are clearly lower than the ones of N within TiN . No available values being given in literature for the self-diffusion coefficient of Ti in TiN , we report the values for the diffusion of Ti within α -Ti and in TiC_{1-x} which is an isostructural phase of TiN . As shown by Gülpen et al. [37,38], the layer kinetic growths directly depend

on those diffusion coefficients as indicated by the Equation 1. This means that in the considering temperature range, the Si₃N₄ growth kinetic is largely lower than the one of TiN despite close Gibbs energies of formation

(at T = 1100°C, $\Delta_f G_{\text{TiN}}^0 = -2.067.105 \text{ J.mol}^{-1}$

and

$\Delta_f G_{\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4}^0 = -3.892.105 \text{ J.mol}^{-1}$).

$$\tilde{D}_{\text{int}} = - \left(N_A \cdot D_B^* + N_B \cdot D_A^* \right) \frac{\Delta_f G_\gamma^0}{R.T} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

with :

\tilde{D}_{int} : the integrated diffusion coefficient of growth of the γ phase,

N_A and N_B mole fraction of species A and B, respectively,

D_A^* and D_B^* : the self diffusion coefficient of species A and B, respectively,

$\Delta_f G_\gamma^0$: the Gibbs energy of formation per mole of the γ phase.

3.2 Effect of the particle size

The influence of the particle size was studied by nitriding two powders with different mean size i.e. 1.4 and 4.5 μm . The so-obtained weight increase during nitridation at 1100°C is largely higher with the smaller particles than with the bigger ones (Fig. 4). Nevertheless, at a temperature of 1000°C the weight increases for the both powders are practically the same, they are equal to 14.29% and 14.60%, respectively. However it must be underlined that, in this case, the smaller particles react with a greater initial rate. Furthermore, at 1100°C a higher conversion rate is reached in a given amount of time. This can be attributed to the increase in the reactive surface area, thereby enhancing the exposure between the TiSi₂ and the nitrogen.

Large particles provide large macropores, but at the expense of decreased surface area. On the other hand, small particles provide increased reactive area for the same void fraction, but lead to smaller macropores which inhibit nitrogen diffusion. This assertion is confirmed by the mass percentage variations of the different phases (Fig. 5). Indeed, regardless of the temperature, the TiSi₂ apparent decomposition kinetic is obviously higher for the

smaller particles. This indicates that, despite the low reaction kinetic of Si₃N₄ formation, the decomposition of the starting phase is increased because of a higher reaction surface leading to the galloping formation of TiN. It also appears that the used of smaller powders facilitate the reaction between silicon and nitrogen especially at 1100°C so much so that free silicon is no more detectable by X-ray diffraction experiments after 50 hours at 1100°C. In the same time, the cumulative mass fractions of α -Si₃N₄ and β -Si₃N₄ reaches a total of 51.4 mass% which is a value largely higher than the other ones obtained for this duration. The corresponding value for the powder with the higher grain size is only of 16.1 mass% with 33.3 mass % of silicon.

3-3 Description of the TiSi₂ nitridation process

On the basis of the results presented above, the nitridation process of TiSi₂ can be described on the base of the study realized by R.G. Pigeon et al. about the nitridation of silicon powders [20]. Indeed, in their work these authors demonstrate that the nitridation of silicon consists of a reaction-bonding process divided into three major stages: (1) initial nucleation/devitrification, (2) massive nitridation, and (3) final nitridation. During the first stage, silicon exposed at the surface of the powder heap is converted into silicon nitride nuclei which are at the origin of a seeding effect inducing the second stage with a fast and massive nitridation rate. During this second stage, nitrogen is able to diffuse freely through the macropores. However, the volume gain induces by the particles nitridation decreases the permeability and consequently slows down the conversion kinetic, what corresponds to the third stage of the silicon conversion process. From our point of view, the same kind of analysis can be applied to the nitridation of TiSi₂ with one major difference: the presence of titanium. TiSi₂ was chosen because of its great volume gain after nitridation equal to 57.0%. Compared to the corresponding value for pure silicone that is 21.6%, the volume increase during TiSi₂ conversion is very larger and evidently generates a dramatically decrease of the permeability of the powder and consequently an intense slowdown of the mass gain. The main difference between the present study and the one of R.G. Pigeon et al. [20] is then a

competition between the nitridation of titanium and silicon. From the results reported above, it is quite clear that the nitridation of titanium is clearly faster in any case and the kinetic gap is especially elevated at 1000°C. Nevertheless, the shapes of the curves are quite similar despite the existence of two different reactions with very different intrinsic kinetics. The consequence of the rapid titanium nitridation is that the lowering of permeability is essentially induced by this reaction. Indeed, the formation of a TiN layer around the grain as it can be seen in the Figure 8 plays the role of a diffusion barrier limiting the nitridation of silicon. As a consequence, a underlying layer of pure silicon is formed under the TiN layer (Fig. 8). At the third stage, the conversion rate is then relatively low but strongly depends on the particles size. Indeed, it appears that a reduction of the mean size of the powder makes possible to reach a conversion rate largely higher because of a more important area of contact between powder and the gas and also because of a reduction of the diffusion distances. In our case, this effect appears to be insufficient to reach rapidly a full conversion. As reported by R.G. Pigeon et al. [20], the compact effects dominate with the formation of a dense product layer on the outer edges of the raw powder. The full conversion is consequently difficult in the case of large sized samples. More clearly, the global conversion rate and the final conversion value strongly depend on the quantity of matter to react. This process is interesting and efficient only in the case of small objects.

Regardless of the application, one possibility to reach a full conversion should be to apply higher temperatures. That is why thermogravimetric analyses were also realized on the two kinds of powder at 1150 and 1200°C up to durations equal to 10h. The results show in the Figure 9 demonstrate that the use of small grain powders is no more interesting from 1200°C, the corresponding mass gain is in this case smaller with the smaller sized powder (30.8%) than with the larger sized one (41.4%). At 1150°C, the values after 10h of nitridation are practically the same: 28.7% for the finer powder and 26.8% for the coarser one. So, it appears that the used of finer powders can induce higher conversion kinetics but the effect is strongly dependant on the temperature. Evidently, the increase of conversion rate with fine powders at high temperatures is conjugate to a negative effect that is

the formation of a dense layer of silicon at the surface of the powder heap preventing diffusion of nitrogen inwardly. So, the use of powders with finer grains size involves identifying the optimum processing temperature in order to limit adverse effects which inhibit the conversion reaction.

4 Conclusion

On the basis of the silicon powders nitridation mechanism reported previously [6], the TiSi₂ powders nitridation process can be described by three different steps: initial nucleation, massive nitridation, final nitridation. The difficulty to reach a full conversion comes from a lowering of permeability because of the rapid nitridation of titanium which generates a noticeable volume gain. Nevertheless, this process is a promising way to product matrix of composites. The research of alternative solution to promote and to facilitate the full conversion should be shortly examined.

Fig. 1. Theory of active filler.

Fig. 2. Calculated isothermal Ti-Si-N diagram at 1373 K [8].

Fig. 3. Evolution of the mass increases at 1000°C of the two kinds of powder with $d_{50}=1.4\mu\text{m}$ and $d_{50}=4.5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the mass increases at 1100°C of the two kinds of powder with $d_{50}=1.4\mu\text{m}$ and $d_{50}=4.5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 5. Phases quantifications by Rietveld method during nitridation of TiSi_2 powders: a) powder with $d_{50}=4.5\mu\text{m}$ at 1000°C, b) powder with $d_{50}=1.4\mu\text{m}$ at 1000°C, c) powder with $d_{50}=4.5\mu\text{m}$ at 1100°C, d) powder with $d_{50}=1.4\mu\text{m}$ at 1100°C.

Fig. 6. Calculated Ti-N phase diagram [8].

Fig. 7. Values from the literature of the self-diffusion coefficients (D^*) of Ti and N in the phase TiN and values for Si and N in the phase Si₃N₄ [30,31,32,33,34]. The values of the self-diffusion coefficients of titanium in α-Ti and in TiC_{1-x} are also given [35,36].

Fig. 8. TiSi₂ grains nitridated at 1100°C during 5h

Fig. 9. Thermogravimetric curves of TiSi_2 at 1000, 1100, 1150 and 1200°C for:
 a) powder with a grain size of about $4.5\mu\text{m}$ and
 b) powder with a grain size of about $1.4\mu\text{m}$.

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